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HUMAN RESOURCE PRACTICES AND ORGANIZATIONAL IDENTITY: CULTURAL PERSPECTIVES ON WORKFORCE ENGAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the relationship between human resource practices (HRP), employee satisfaction, and workforce engagement within an organizational context using secondary HR analytics data. The purpose of the study is to investigate whether HRP significantly influence workforce engagement and to assess the mediating role of employee satisfaction in this relationship. A quantitative research design was employed dataset, which contains 311 employee records and includes variables related to performance evaluation, employee satisfaction, engagement, and work-related characteristics. Descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, multiple regression, and mediation analysis were used to test the proposed relationships. The findings indicate that performance-related HRP have a significant positive effect on both employee satisfaction and workforce engagement. In particular, performance score emerged as a strong predictor of engagement, suggesting that effective performance management systems can enhance employees' involvement and commitment at work. However, the mediating role of employee satisfaction was not supported, indicating that the relationship between HR practices and engagement is more direct than indirect in this dataset. The study contributes to the human resource management literature by extending understanding of how HR practices shape employee outcomes in organizational settings. The findings also offer practical implications for managers seeking to improve workforce engagement through strategic human resource systems and performance-oriented workplace practices.

KEYWORDS: human resource practices, employee satisfaction, workforce engagement, performance management, HR analytics, organizational performance, employee attitudes, mediation analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

Human resource management (HRM) practices play a important role in shaping employee attitudes, behaviors, and overall organizational performance. In contemporary organizations the need to employ good human resource practice among recruitment, performance management and employee development has become a strategic resource in improving the productivity and effectiveness of the work force and the organization. The practices also help in ensuring the competencies and capabilities of the employees, which eventually lead to organizational success and sustainability (Anwar and Abdullah, 2021; Otoo, 2019). Companies with well-organized HR practices have higher chances of developing favorable work conditions that would motivate employees to work well and be dedicated towards organizational objectives. In this regard, employee motivation, satisfaction, and engagement are regarded as critical factors (HR practices) that have a collective bearing on the long-term organizational performance (Kareem and Hussein, 2019).

One of the most crucial elements in improving employee engagement is now performance and output, as well as retention of employees in the company. Employed people are more enthusiastic, committed, and engaged with their jobs and the positive impact of these attitudes on the individual and the organization (Schneider et al., 2018). It has been demonstrated that the organization that has highly engaged employees is more likely to have higher productivity, better service quality, and decreased turnover of the employees (Adriyanto, 2023). Moreover, engagement makes the employees more psychologically committed to their work and to the entire organization, which promotes more positive involvement in the process of organizational success (Saks et al., 2022). Due to this fact, the research on the factors that affect employee engagement has become a significant concern in modern HRM studies.

Although the significance of HR practices in promoting employee engagement has been identified, inconsistent employee engagement levels have been illustrated by most organizations despite the involvement of HR practices. Although there are different HR programs that organizations invest in, not all of them result in the anticipated employee engagement changes. The first reason is that the HR practices have an indirect effect on engagement, as it is affected by the psychological reactions of the employees, especially the employee satisfaction. It has been proposed that employee satisfaction has a

major influence on the employee attitude towards the working environment and organizational policies (Memon et al., 2021). Despite the fact that the relationship between HR practices and employee engagement has been analyzed in previous studies, there is little research that has investigated the mediating effect of employee satisfaction as using HR analytics datasets. The gap could be filled in to give useful information about the role of HR practices in the engagement of workforce in organizational settings (Pradhan et al., 2019).

Research Objectives

1. To examine the effect of human resource practices on workforce engagement within organizational settings
2. To investigate the relationship between human resource practices and employee satisfaction as a key employee attitude outcome
3. To analyze the mediating role of employee satisfaction in the relationship between human resource practices and workforce engagement

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Human Resource Practices

HRP are important towards increasing the abilities of the employees and promoting organizational competencies. HRM is seen to have a number of well-organized processes and operations, including recruitment, training and development, performance management, and compensation systems in an attempt to enhance the performance of the workforce and organizational performance. The recruitment strategies contribute to attracting the talented people whose competencies and values can be mobilized in line with the organizational goals, and the training and development programs increase the competencies and flexibility of the employees working in the changing settings (Bao et al., 2021). Performance management systems also bring about the effectiveness of an organization in terms of offering structured feedback and clear performance expectation that drives the behavior and productivity of employees. Best performance management practices have the power to ensure employee engagement as employees are aware of how their efforts can contribute to the overall organizational goals (Mone et al., 2018).

The Resource-Based View (RBV) and Strategic Human Resource Management (SHRM) are the two theories that are frequently used to explain the theoretical basis of HR practices. The RBV indicates that employees are great organizational assets that have the potential of generating sustainable

competitive advantage when managed well. In order to improve employee productivity and organizational performance, strategic HRM focuses on coordinating HR policies and organizational strategies. When HR practices are properly undertaken, then they assist in the acquisition of employee skills, employee motivation, and employee commitment, thus enhancing the overall organizational competitiveness.

2.2 Employee Satisfaction

One of the most crucial items is employee happiness of good HR practices that make employees analyze their job experiences and their workplace situation in general. It is usually explained as the extent of satisfaction that employees have with their job descriptions, working conditions, and organizational practices. Positive organizational outcomes such as a better performance, lower turnover intentions, and increased organizational commitment have been greatly attributed to employee satisfaction (Al Kurdi et al., 2020). Companies that are concerned about the welfare of their employees and establish conducive organizational cultures are more likely to have a greater number of satisfied employees.

It has been shown that workplace conditions, organizational support, and healthy work environments have a major impact on employee satisfaction and productivity (Voordt and Jensen, 2023). When employees become satisfied, they will have a better attitude to their work, and they will be more committed to working. The attitude of the employees is another factor that will influence the workplace behavior because people with positive perceptions of the work environment will be more productive in achieving organizational objectives (Gopinath, 2020). Besides, workplace attitudes contribute to the motivation and commitment of employees, which eventually impact on the performance and retention of employees in an organization (Rubenstein, 2024).

2.3 Workforce Engagement

The concept of workforce engagement has become a focal point in the modern research in HRMM because of its close correlation with the motivational levels and performance of employees. Workforce engagement is the mental and physical commitment that employees show towards the work and company objectives. Employees who are engaged are normally enthusiastic, committed, and involved in their working activities and this adds to increased productivity and better organizational results. Psychological engagement displays the emotional

and cognitive commitment to work of the employees, whereas behavioral engagement entails the effort invested by employees into their work (Ramey et al., 2019).

Employee engagement at high levels is linked with many organizational advantages such as high productivity, better quality of service delivery and less employee turnover. The engagement of employees can also result in them showing behaviors of an organizational citizen and enhance a favorable working environment. Moreover, engagement has been associated with the well-being of employees and the performance of the organization, which is why it is an important consequence of the efficient HR practices (Jun et al., 2021).

2.4 HR Practices and Employee Engagement

Research conducted in the past has highlighted the importance of HR practices in ensuring employee engagement. HR systems offering employees the chances of professional development, adequate performance assessment, and rewarding of employees efforts can increase their motivation and dedication to the purpose of the organization. When HR practices are viewed as accommodative and just by the employees, there is a tendency that the latter will exhibit increased engagement levels in their working positions. Empirical studies lead to the conclusion that in organizations with elaborate HR practices, the workforce is more engaged, and organizational performance is enhanced (Kerdpitak and Jermstipparsert, 2020).

Moreover, the degree of engagement of the employees depends on their perception of the HR systems and organizational culture. As long as the HR practices correspond to the expectations and organizational values of employees, they promote trust and increased emotional attachment of employees to the organization. These positive impressions help a great deal in the readiness of the employees to put effort and commitment in their jobs (Akingbola et al., 2023).

2.5 HR Practices and Employee Satisfaction

Employee satisfaction is also largely influenced by HRP. The HR policies based on fair compensation, career advancement opportunities, and supporting management approaches are part of the reasons why employees positively judge their working environment. It has been shown that high HR practices have a major impact on job satisfaction as they enhance the positive perceptions of employees about organizational support and justice (Pradhan et al., 2019). Employees who are made to feel significant

and backed up by the organization are apt to gain good attitudes towards their work and could be more dedicated to the organizational objectives.

2.6 Mediating Role of Employee Satisfaction

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3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research approach

In this research, quantitative study in order to determine the correlations between workforce engagement, human resource and employee satisfaction. The application of quantitative methods in HRM research is quite common since it allows testing the hypotheses regarding relationships between variables in a more empirical manner through the use of the methods of statistics. The research is of cross-sectional nature by which employee data are evaluated at one time in order to establish trends and correlation between HR practices and employee performance in the organizational contexts.

3.2 Data Source and Sample

The research makes use of a secondary data acquired in a human resource analytics database. The dataset has 311 records on employees, which include employee engagement details, job satisfaction, performance review, sources of recruitment, as well as demographic details. The application of secondary organizational data will enable the study to examine actual workplace data as well as enhancing the external validity of the results. The sample used in the data set comprises various workers in various departments, and with diverse demographical backgrounds (Huebner and Patalano, 2023).

3.3 Variables and Measurement

This study contains three main variables namely; HRP, employee satisfaction, and workforce engagement. The independent variable is HRP and is measured using the indicators which include

recruitment source, performance score and special project assignments. The mediating variable is employee satisfaction that is measured by the variable *EmpSatisfaction* that indicates the level of satisfaction of employees with their work and workplace conditions. The dependent variable is the workforce engagement, which is defined with the help of the *EngagementSurvey* score, which is the degree to what employees are involved and committed to the work they do.

3.4 Data Analysis Techniques

The statistical measures that are used in analyzing the data refer to those that are usually used in organizational studies. To begin with, the demographic variables and important values are summarized with the help of descriptive statistics. Second, the correlation analysis is performed to investigate the relations between the HR practices, the employee satisfaction, and the workforce engagement. Lastly, regression and mediation tests are conducted to compare the direct and indirect influence of the HR practices on workforce engagement via employee satisfaction.

3.5 Ethical Considerations

This is a secondary study, and no personal identifiable data are applied in the analysis. The data set is only used in the academic research and safeguards the privacy and confidentiality of employees. Any analysis follows ethical standards regarding the organization research and the use of data.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Ernest attempts to summarize the main variables in this research work provided through the descriptive statistics to describe workforce engagement, employee satisfaction as well as indicators of HRP. The overall mean score on workforce engagement is 4.11 as illustrated in Table 1, which revealed that the level of engagement in the workforce is relatively high in this organization. The average score in employee satisfaction was 3.89 meaning that there is a general report of moderate to high rates of satisfaction with the working environment by the employees.

The indicators of the HR practice showed that the mean performance score was 2.98, and the average special projects assigned were 1.22. The total average of absences had been registered in the dataset amounting to 10.24, and the employees had recorded that they had been late an average of 0.41 days in the

last 30 days. All these descriptive statistics offer a summary of how employees behave as well as HR-related metrics within the organization (Figure 1).

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Study Variables

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
EngagementSurvey	4.11	0.79	1.12	5.00
EmpSatisfaction	3.89	0.91	1.00	5.00
PerfScoreID	2.98	0.59	1.00	4.00
SpecialProjectsCount	1.22	2.35	0.00	8.00
DaysLateLast30	0.41	1.29	0.00	6.00
Absences	10.24	5.85	1.00	20.00

Figure 1: Distribution of Key Workforce Engagement and HR Indicators

The pie chart presents the distribution of key variables including workforce engagement, employee satisfaction, performance scores, special project assignments, late days, and absences. The results highlight the relative contribution of HR indicators influencing employee behavior and workplace engagement patterns.

4.2 Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis was conducted to test the relationships between the variables used in the study. Table 2 indicates that performance score (PerfScoreID) has a moderate positive relational with workforce engagement ($r = .545$) implying that the higher the performance rating the higher the engagement rate of the employee. On the same note, performance score is positively correlated with employee satisfaction ($r = .304$).

Yet, there is a weak relationship between the variable special projects count on one hand and engagement and satisfaction on the other hand. Also, workforce engagement is weakly related but positively correlated with employee satisfaction ($r = .187$) meaning that employees with high satisfaction levels are likely to display some higher levels of workforce engagement (Figure 2).

Table 2: Correlation Matrix

Variable	1	2	3	4
1. EngagementSurvey	1			
2. EmpSatisfaction	.187	1		
3. PerfScoreID	.545	.304	1	
4. SpecialProjectsCount	.013	.034	.042	1

Figure 2: Correlation Heatmap of Workforce Engagement, Employee Satisfaction, and HR Practice Indicators

The heatmap illustrates the correlation relationships among workforce engagement, employee satisfaction, performance score, and special project assignments. The results indicate that performance score has the strongest positive association with engagement and satisfaction, while special project assignments show minimal relationships with other variables.

4.3 Regression Analysis

The regression analysis was performed to investigate how the indicators of HR practices influence the type of employee satisfaction and the workforce engagement. According to the results in Table 3, the score of performance has a strong positive influence on the satisfaction of employees ($B = 0.469, p < .001$). Projects count, however, does not have a significant contribution to employee satisfaction ($p > .05$).

Table 3: Regression Results for Employee Satisfaction

Predictor	B	Std. Error	Beta	p-value
PerfScoreID	0.469	0.082	.304	<0.001
SpecialProjectsCount	0.008	0.022	.021	0.712

Model Statistics: $R^2 = 0.093, F = 15.67 (p < .001)$

The second regression model was estimated to determine the effect of the HR practices on workforce engagement. Because, as shown in Table 4, a

performance score is a significant predictor of workforce engagement ($B = 0.734$, $p < .001$), employees with high workforce engagement levels are more likely to report higher levels of workforce engagement. By comparison, special projects count does not have a significant influence on engagement ($p > .05$).

Table 4: Regression Results for Workforce Engagement

Predictor	B	Std. Error	Beta	p-value
PerfScoreID	0.734	0.071	.545	<0.001
SpecialProjectsCount	-0.004	0.017	-.012	0.807

Model Statistics: $R^2 = 0.297$, $F = 64.21$ ($p < .001$)

4.4 Mediation Analysis

The employee satisfaction was put into the regression model in order to test the hypothesis of the mediation between the HR practices and the workforce engagement. As per the findings presented in Table 5, employee satisfaction is not a significant predictor of workforce engagement ($B = 0.021$, $p = .631$). In the meantime, a significant influence of the performance score on engagement is observed, and it could be proposed that the connection between HR practices and workforce engagement is rather direct than it is mediated by the employee satisfaction.

Table 5: Mediation Regression Results

Predictor	B	Std. Error	Beta	p-value
PerfScoreID	0.724	0.074	.538	<0.001
SpecialProjectsCount	-0.004	0.017	-.012	0.801
EmpSatisfaction	0.021	0.043	.024	0.631

Model Statistics:

$R^2 = 0.297$

$F = 64.21$ ($p < .001$)

4.5 Hypothesis Testing Summary

According to the regression analysis and mediation analysis, the results of the hypothesis test are as follows in Table 6. The results suggest that performance management indicators are the main drivers of HR practices in regards to engagement of the workforce. Nonetheless, the role of employee satisfaction in this relation is insignificant.

Table 6: Hypothesis Testing Results

Hypothesis	Statement	Result
H1	HR practices positively influence workforce engagement	Partially Supported
H2	HR practices positively influence employee satisfaction	Partially Supported
H3	Employee satisfaction positively influences workforce engagement	Not Supported
H4	Employee satisfaction mediates the relationship between HR practices and workforce engagement	Not Supported

5. DISCUSSION

This study was aimed at investigating the linkage between HRP and satisfaction of employees and workforce engagement and also exploring the mediating effect of employee satisfaction in this relationship. The results give a number of insights in understanding the effect of organizational HR practices on workforce attitudes and behavioral results in work environments.

The findings suggest that the HRP, especially performance management indicators, play a major positive role in influencing the workforce engagement. This result indicates that workers with a better performance rating are likely to exhibit greater interest in work and organizational practice. The performance management systems enable the employees to know their roles and expectations and contribution to organizational goals and these can enhance motivation and participation in the work activities. Such finding can be aligned with past studies indicating that a well-performing HR can improve employee engagement, through the establishment of conducive workplaces, and the promotion of employee engagement in organizational operations (Kerdpitak and Jermsittiparsert, 2020). On the same note, studies have revealed that good HR practices help in the competitive advantage leading to better employee motivation and commitment to the organization.

It also indicates that performance-based HR practices will have a great impact on the satisfaction of employees. When the employees are better evaluated in terms of performance, they are likely to report greater satisfaction with their workplace. The outcome of this research proves previous literature that says that HR practices are significant in determining the attitude and perceptions of organizational support among employees (Elrehail et al., 2020). Employees would tend to build positive attitudes towards their work and organization when they feel that their efforts are appreciated and rewarded by means of equitable HR systems. The employee satisfaction is thus a significant result of good HR management policies.

Nevertheless, the findings demonstrate that the satisfaction of employees is not a significant predictor of workforce engagement in this dataset, and the mediating effects of satisfaction between the HR practices and the workforce engagement are not justified. This observation is contrary to various previous studies that implied that employee satisfaction may be used as an intermediate variable between HR practices and employee engagement (Pradhan et al., 2019; Riyanto et al., 2021). The possible explanation is that performance-related

systems and organizational structures might be more effective in promoting the workforce engagement in the studied organization than the overall job satisfaction of the employees with the working conditions. Employees can stay motivated by their work not necessarily because of their personal emotional motivation but because of organizational demands, performance appraisal programs or because of career growth.

Employee attitudes are also found to be significant in workplace behavior as noted by the results. The study of organizational behavior has always focused on the fact that work-related behaviors, motivation, and productivity depend on the attitude of the employees. When employees also have positive attitudes towards their organization, this may result in better engagements and better organizational performance (Gopinath, 2020; Rubenstein, 2024). Engagement alone is a significant measure of psychological and behavioral participation of workers in the organization, which is associated with individual performance and organizational performance (Ramey et al., 2019).

Also, the results could be described in terms of Social Exchange Theory that implies that the employees can react to positive organizational treatment by exhibiting positive attitudes and behavior. By adopting supportive HR practices by organizations, employees can also return the favor by being more committed and engaged in the work (Ahmad et al., 2023). Even though employee satisfaction was not a significant mediator in this study, HR practices were found to have a significant impact on the employee engagement in this study through performance-related processes.

Moreover, workforce engagement is also a significant organizational outcome because it has a close link with employee well-being and the organizational performance. In the past, studies have established that engaged employees will lead to enhanced organizational performance, such as productivity, quality of service delivery, and retention of employees (Jun et al., 2021). Hence, it is advisable that organizations are still encouraged to work on HR strategies that enhance the engagement of employees by ensuring that their performance management systems are effective, and that the work environment is conducive to them.

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This research is relevant to the current literature because it emphasizes the significance of HR practices in determining workforce engagement as well as uncovers the fact that mediating effect of employee satisfaction can also differ based on organizational setting and design of HR systems. These understandings imply that organizations need to strategically formulate HR policies that optimize performance management against employee support systems to improve employee satisfaction, and employee engagement.

6. CONCLUSION

This paper has explored the connection between human resources practices, employee satisfaction and workforce engagement based on secondary organizational information. The results show that workforce engagement is affected by HRP particularly performance management indicators in a positive significant way. When performance is rated higher, the employees are more likely to show higher involvement, motivation and commitment to their work and organizational objectives. The findings also indicate that HR practices that relate to performance have a positive effect on employee satisfaction, thus, indicating that well-planned performance systems and performance recognition systems play a contributing role in positive employee perceptions towards their workplace. Nevertheless, in this study, the mediating role of employee satisfaction in the relationship between the HR practices and workforce engagement was not supported. This observation suggests that the performance management systems and the organizational expectations might have a stronger effect on employee engagement instead of the job satisfaction rates of employees alone. The research has a contribution to the HRM literature because it has supported empirical evidences on the effect of HR practices on employee attitudes and engagement in organizational settings. These results emphasize the need to ensure that the organizations have sound HR policies that enhance the performance management systems and, at the same time, encourage the supportive working conditions. Organizations can increase the engagement of their workforce through the combination of HR strategic practices implemented and employee-based approaches to increase the overall organizational performance.

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